

УДК 62-523.8

TO THE PROBLEM OF TV INNOVATIONS IN THE NEAR FUTURE

К ПРОБЛЕМЕ ТЕЛЕВИЗИОННЫХ ИННОВАЦИЙ В БЛИЖАЙШЕМ БУДУЩЕМ

©Gavrilova A.

*Astrakhan State Technical University
Astrakhan, Russia
nastusha5565@mail.ru*

©Гаврилова А. С.

*Астраханский государственный технический университет
г. Астрахань, Россия
nastusha5565@mail.ru*

©Grigoryeva M.

*Astrakhan State Technical University
Astrakhan, Russia
marina_grig05@mail.ru*

©Григорьева М. А.

*Астраханский государственный технический университет
г. Астрахань, Россия
marina_grig05@mail.ru*

Abstract. This article describes the innovation in technology services. In the process the information about some new and improved gadgets was received. Today this area is evolving and the article discusses three new inventions that will help all mankind in the future. This theme is most relevant to the technical specialists, or people who are fond of TV.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена инновациям в сфере технологических услуг. В процессе работы были получены сведения о новых и улучшенных гаджетах. На сегодняшний день эта сфера развивается, и в статье рассматриваются три новых изобретения, которые в будущем помогут всему человечеству. Эта тема наиболее актуальна для людей технических специальностей, либо людей увлекающихся телевидением.

Keywords: innovations, improved gadgets, technical inventions, robots.

Ключевые слова: инновации, улучшенные гаджеты, технические изобретения, роботы.

One of the most important achievements in the world is the invention of television. This innovation has enabled a quick transfer of interesting and relevant information across the world. Today, television has a huge impact on all people, because we use it almost every day. Thanks to the device we can watch different programs and have many new things to learn, beginning from the news, various political programs and ending with programs for children and adolescents.

Telecommunication is growing rapidly today. Image quality (sharpness and brightness of it), is improving as well as new gadgets (such as 3-D glasses) are appearing.

Special television modems are more and more widespread today. With their help each person can record any program and watch it later, as well as to stop it for a certain time. This innovation is useful for busy parents who can choose certain channels with cartoons for children and not to worry about what their children may switch into.

One of the new kinds of television broadcasting is a transition to a newer digital television technology. So, CD technology improves sound quality, and DTV transmits any TV program with

cinematic picture quality. Each subscriber has an access to these technologies. To use these services, you should connect to the DTV format.

Today “High Definition Television” is coming to the top as well. This technology is the most advanced and high-tech area of digital television. This TV provides an unusually bright and clear image without distorting the sound, and is used with multi-channel support. “High Definition Television” supports HDTV standards (1080i and 720p), has a wide-screen 16:9 image.

One way or another, we want to make a forecast of the future of television. And do not think that television is dying as the years go by, due to the influx of new media. For example, TV in its time has not eclipsed the theater.

Still, technology doesn't rest on, and scientists are trying to introduce newer technologies in its line of products. So, we would like to say about the most interesting ideas.

1. Nowadays it is the theme of robots and various assistants that is really developed in Japan. One of these assistants is a robot TV presenter, who has already broadcasted on different television channels in Japan. To begin with, we would like to say that scientists have created several robots with different appearances. These unique creatures could speak in different voices with a wide range of tones, as well as they had a function to switch to any language and volume. For deaf people, robot-presenters showed gestures that could be easily recognized. This innovation is very convenient, as the text is clearly said, in the settings you can enable gestures, as well as the exterior of each person can be chosen for yourself. Robot-presenters are gradually being introduced in other countries. In the near future we'll see different technological creations, which will help people to understand and remember the information better and to record the data, so that we can use it at any time.

2. One of the exciting technologies that was portended by science fiction writers in the twentieth century — is transferring of perfume at a distance, among other things via television and Internet. Unfortunately, over the past decade, the situation has not changed and significant implementations of this idea has not occurred.

In recent years, scientists and engineers are working on this topic for a successful bid in the transmission of TV odors. One such innovation is the new technology of Smell-o-Vision, which has been developed by researchers from the University of Tokyo. It is to install small fans on the four sides of the TV. They will be connected to the flavor capsules that will emit different odors under a certain heating. And a signal that they will receive will dramatically promote heating and flow rate.

3. One of the relevant topics of technologists at this stage — is to improve the quality of the picture and its three-dimensional image. Increasingly, there are TVs that support HDTV and 3-D content. There are also a variety of 3-D panels, which help us to get 3-D effects at home. This topic is relevant, as the market requires more equipment for these formats. The set will have special 3-D glasses that will help watching certain programs on TV. Now, this innovation can be seen in many cinemas, and we can feel the realism and sharpness of the image.

Important factors include the formation of television technology (increased computing power of digital systems and bandwidth data channels) and system - interactivity as a manifestation of feedback. People need gadgets that will ensure the correct and fast feedback under all conditions of communication.

Nowadays, there is a program grid for which each channel transmits the content stream to the subscriber. These services can be used on request and at the request of the customer. For example: “request for video”, “request for the program”. Today, many software engineers try to improve the grid and create special “smart playlists” which allow feedback and improvement of image quality. This system monitors the tastes and preferences of the customer and forms programs on his preferences, the customer can also choose a theme that he is interested in and “play list” will show the selected programs. As a result, the advertising model is changed. Advertising is specialized and is now delivered only to the useful subscribers.

Today this topic is very essential, because all people use television, both on the phone and other gadgets. With new innovations we will be able to obtain unique technologies, such as flying gadgets, or the effect of odor that will make our lives more different. The most important thing today is not to stop and continue to develop.

References:

1. Ainalieva A. R. The role of analysis in the text translation at technical universities. International scientific–practical conference “Theoretical and practical aspects of linguistics, literature, teaching methodology, translation and intercultural communication”: materials / ed. M. G. Golubeva, E. V. Kuznetsova, 2014, pp. 110–114.
2. Fedorova O. V., Grigoryeva M. A., Nurmuhambetova S. A. English in the field of oil and gas industry: textbook, Astrakhan, ASTU, 2014, pp. 64-65.
3. Kochegarova N. A. Analysis of teaching methods and individual strategies of mastering foreign languages. *Psikhologiya i pedagogika: metodika i problemy prakticheskogo primeneniya*, 2010, no. 16–2. Pp. 278–282.

Список литературы:

1. Ainalieva A. R. The role of analysis in the text translation at technical universities // Международная научно–практическая конференция «Теоретические и практические аспекты лингвистики, литературоведения, методики преподавания, перевода и межкультурной коммуникации»: материалы / под ред. М. Г. Голубевой, Е. В. Кузнецовой. 2014. С. 110–114.
2. Федорова О. В., Григорьева М. А., Нурмухамбетова С. А. Английский язык в сфере нефтяной и газовой промышленности: учебное пособие. Астрахань: Изд-во АГТУ, 2014. С. 64–65.
3. Кочегарова Н. А. Анализ методов обучения и индивидуальных стратегий усвоения иностранных языков // Психология и педагогика: методика и проблемы практического применения. 2010. №16–2. С. 278–282.

*Работа поступила в редакцию
17.04.2016 г.*

*Принята к публикации
20.04.2016 г.*